

Naphthyridines Reactivity of Methyl Groups : New Cyanine Dyes from 2, 7-Dimethyl- and 4, 7-Dimethyl-1, 8-Naphthyridines

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The reactivity of the methyl groups in 2, 7-dimethyl- and 4, 7-dimethyl-1, 8-naphthyridine is discussed. The preparation of new cyanine dyes is described. The centre of basicity and structures of dyes have been established.

THE comparative reactivity of the two methyl groups in 4, 7-dimethyl-1, 8-naphthyridine (3) has been studied by two methods. Firstly, the base (3) was condensed with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in boiling toluene, using a water separator. The styryl compound thus obtained was oxidised with potassium permanganate, in acetone, to give a carboxylic acid which on decarboxylation furnished 2-methyl-1, 8-naphthyridine (1). Thus it was clear that the aldehyde had reacted with the 4-methyl group of the base (3) and this fact established its higher reactivity in comparison to the 7-methyl group.

The above conclusion was also confirmed from a study of the absorption spectra of several new cyanine and styryl dyes prepared from (2) and (3). The absorption maxima of all these dyes are recorded in Table 1. It is apparent that trimethin cyanines (27) to (32), derived from (3), possess absorption maxima at much longer wave length than the corresponding trimethin cyanines (15) to (20) derived from (2). Likewise the mono- and di-styryl dyes from (3) have absorption maxima at longer wave length than those from (2). This large bathochromic shift indicates a longer methin chain in the dyes derived from (3), which is only possible when the dyes are formed by the reaction of the 4-methyl group and the quaternisation is at N₁. The presence of a new absorption maxima around 310 m μ in the dyes derived from (3), which is absent in the dyes prepared from (2), also supports the above view. Dyes from 2, 4, dimethyl-7-acetamido-1, 8-naphthyridine have been reported¹ but their structures do not appear to be fully established.

The bases 2,7-dimethyl-(2) and 4,7-dimethyl-1, 8-naphthyridine (3) and their quaternary salts (5) to (8) were prepared in the usual way². Even forcing conditions failed to quaternise the second nitrogen N₈. This is in line with earlier reports^{3,4}. The

deeper colour of the quaternary salts may be due to sharing of the positive charge^{5,6} by N₁ and N₈. The trimethin cyanine dyes (27) to (32) were prepared by reaction of the anilino vinyl derivative (25) and (26) with the appropriate heterocyclic quaternary salts. The styryl dyes (23) and (24) were obtained by heating the salts (7) and (8) with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in acetic anhydride. Similarly, dyes (11), (12) and (15) to (20) were prepared from (2) following the above procedure.

The di-styryl compounds (21), (22), (33) and (34) were obtained when a mixture of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and the corresponding quaternary salt was boiled in absolute alcohol in presence of triethylamine. At first, the solution turned deep red, as the boiling continued the colour slowly changed to deep blue and finally a blue dye separated. Analytical results confirmed that these are di-styryl compounds.

It is suggested that the formation of the di-styryl dye is completed in two stages. In the first stage, a mono styryl red dye is produced which activates the 7-methyl group in the following manner:

Thus the carbanion at the 7-position, formed by treating with triethylamine, a strong base, can be easily accounted for. This carbanion then reacts with another molecule of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde to give the blue di-styryl dye. This is a unique case of activation of a methyl group by a

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TABLE-1

Serial No. of Compound	Nature of R	Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	Nature of R ₃	M.P. °C	% of yield	Physical Characteristic	max mμ	% of Found	Nitrogen Calc.
1.	-	-CH ₃	H	H	99-100	20	White cottony needles	-	-	-
2.	-	-CH ₃	H	-CH ₃	194-95	50	White needles	-	-	-
3.	-	H	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	84-86	30	do	-	-	-
4.	CH ₃	-CH ₃	H	H	165-67	81	Greenish yellow needles	-	-	-
5.	CH ₃	-CH ₃	H	-CH ₃	234-35	96.4	Yellow needles	-	9.33	9.34
6.	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	H	-CH ₃	209-10	80	Greenish yellow needles	-	8.62	8.91
7.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	211	71	Brown needles	-	9.33	9.14
8.	C ₂ H ₅	H	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	145	63	Deep brown needles	-	8.77	8.91
9.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	285	70	Royal blue small needles	-	-	-
10.	CH ₃	H	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	H	275	72	Green needles with golden reflex	-	-	-
11.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	H	-CH ₃	244-45	98	Steel blue needles	220 542	9.92	9.74
12.	C ₂ H ₅	do	H	-CH ₃	240	90	do	-	-	-
13.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-NH.C ₆ H ₅	H	-CH ₃	249-50	55	Red needles	-	10.17	10.04
14.	C ₂ H ₅	do	H	-CH ₃	219-20	52	Red needles	-	9.89	10.07
15.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-CH=2-(1-methylquinoline)	H	-CH ₃	276-77	84	Dark blue needles	225 601	8.72	8.98
16.	C ₂ H ₅	-CH=CH-CH=2-(1-ethylquinoline)	H	-CH ₃	304-5	80	do	218 610	8.25	8.48
17.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-CH=4-(1-methylquinoline)	H	-CH ₃	259-60	85	Blue needles	225 640	8.67	8.98
18.	C ₂ H ₅	-CH=CH-CH=4-(1-ethylquinoline)	H	-CH ₃	190	76	Blue needles	228 647	8.31	8.48
19.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-CH=2-(1-methylbenzothiazole)	H	-CH ₃	245	88	Royal blue needles	225 580	8.89	9.11
20.	C ₂ H ₅	-CH=CH-CH=2-(1-ethylbenzothiazole)	H	-CH ₃	277	85	Royal blue needles	222 582	8.38	8.58
21.	CH ₃	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ .N.(CH ₃) ₂	H	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ .N.(CH ₃) ₂	288-90	22.5	Small blue crystals	223 602	9.77	9.96
22.	C ₂ H ₅	do	H	do	320	25	do	-	-	-
23.	CH ₃	H	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	-CH ₃	278	83	Green shining needles	225 320 560	9.49	9.74
24.	C ₂ H ₅	H	do	-CH ₃	245	80	do	-	-	-
25.	CH ₃	H	-CH=CH-NH-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃	256	66	Red needles	-	9.84	10.04
26.	C ₂ H ₅	H	do	-CH ₃	210	61	do	-	9.79	10.07
27.	CH ₃	H	-CH=CH-CH=2-(1-methylquinoline)	-CH ₃	261	58	Deep blue needles	225 317 648	8.69	8.98

TABLE I (Contd)

28.	C ₂ H ₅	H	-CH = CH-CH = 2-(1-ethylquinoline)	-CH ₃	260	65	Blue shining needles	225 308 650	8.27	8.48
29.	CH ₃	H	-CH = CH-CH = 4-(1-methylquinoline)	-CH ₃	291	90	Blue needles with golden reflex	223 310 690	8.27	8.98
30.	C ₂ H ₅	H	-CH = CH-CH = 4-(1-ethylquinoline)	-CH ₃	260	84	Shining blue needles	223 310 698	8.24	8.48
31.	CH ₃	H	-CH = CH-CH = 2-(1-methylbenzothiazole)	-CH ₃	240	60	Coal black needles	225 300 550 628	8.79	9.11
32.	C ₂ H ₅	H	-CH = CH-CH = 2-(1-ethylbenzothiazole)	-CH ₃	270	65	Dark black needles	225 308 630 710	8.34	8.58
33.	CH ₃	H	-CH = CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	-CH = CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	320	21	Deep blue small crystals	224 320 580 708	9.63	9.96
34.	C ₂ H ₅	H	do	do	320	22	do	-	-	-

styryl moiety which does not appear to have been observed earlier. The above mechanism is in line with current views⁷ and holds good when the methyl groups are at 4- and 7-positions.

It appears that the sharing of the positive charge between N₁ and N₈ does not activate the 7-methyl group. This view receives support from the fact that the quaternary salts failed to give the corresponding di-anilino vinyl derivative, upon fusion with diphenylformamidine under a variety of conditions. In each case only the mono anilino vinyl derivative (13), (14), (25) and (26) could be prepared.

All the trimethin cyanines were tested for their sensitising effect by admixture with silver halide emulsion and all were found to be useless as sensitisers. It is suggested that the lone pair electrons on N₈ interfere and complete delocalisation along the trimethin chain is thus inhibited, resulting in loss of sensitising property :

Experimental

All m. ps. are uncorrected. The experimental conditions described are typical of the general methods of synthesis followed in this work. All compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

2,7-Dimethyl-1,8-naphthyridine(2). : This was prepared by a modification of Paudler's method⁸.

Sulpho Mixture⁸. Nitrobenzene (49.5 g) was sulphonated by running it into 20% oleum (220 g) at

20-30° and then the mixture was heated, with stirring, at 60-70° for 3-4 hrs. The mixture was maintained at this temperature until a sample was completely soluble in water.

Sulpho mixture (117 g), water (45 ml) and 2-amino-6-methylpyridine (8.6g) were taken in a flask and to this crotonaldehyde (19.0g) was added dropwise during 30 mts. With constant stirring, the temperature being maintained at 110-20°. After the addition was complete, the stirring was continued for another 5 mts. It was then cooled in ice bath and made alkaline with conc. NaOH solution and filtered (solid A). The filtrate was extracted with chloroform (4 times, 100 ml, each). The combined chloroform extract was then extracted four times with HCl solution (100 ml. each time, pH 1-2). The pH of the acid solution was adjusted to 5-6 and it was then extracted again with chloroform (4 times, 100 ml.). The combined chloroform extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to dryness, giving brownish needles (3.2 g) m. p. 190-94° (Lit¹. 194-95°).

The solid A was triturated with chloroform (twice, 100 ml) and extracted with HCl solution pH 1-2). The aqueous layer was taken and its pH adjusted to 5-6, and then extracted with chloroform (4 times, 50 ml). The chloroform solution was dried (Na₂SO₄) and then evaporated to give a solid (1g), m.p. 188-93°. This was sublimed to give white needles m.p. 194-95°. Total yield 4.2g.

2, 7-Dimethyl-1,8-naphthyridine-N₁-methioide (5)-2,7-dimethyl-1,8-naphthyridine (2) (0.6g) was taken in dry benzene (25 ml) and to this methyl iodide (2 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. on waterbath, cooled and the solids(1.1g) filtered. Yellow needles with greenish tinge m.p. 234-35° (Ethanol). (Found : C, 45.7 ; H, 4.5 ; N, 9.34 ; I, 42.01. C₁₁H₁₃N₂I requires C, 44.0 ; H, 4.33 ; N, 9.33 ; I, 44.33%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-7-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-N₁-methiodide (11) : An intimate mixture of (5) (0.15g) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.075g) was taken in acetic anhydride (5 ml) and refluxed for 30 mts., cooled and the solid filtered (0.21g), m.p. 244-45° (ethanol), steel blue needles. (Found : C, 55.5 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 9.92 ; C₂₀H₂₂N₃I requires C, 55.68 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 9.74%).

2,7-Di-p-dimethylaminostyryl-1, 8-naphthyridine-N₁-methiodide(21) : An intimate mixture of (5)(0.15g) and *p*-dimethylanminobenzaldehyde (0.15g) was taken in (ethanol) (5 ml) and heated to dissolve the solids, triethylamine (1 ml) was added to the hot solution and then refluxed for 2 hrs., cooled and the solid filtered (0.18 g) It was repeatedly triturated with hot ethanol. Blue tiny needles, m.p. 288-90° (ethanol). (Found : C, 61.60 ; H, 5.91 ; N, 9.77. C₂₀H₂₁N₄I requires C, 61.90 ; H, 5.61 ; N, 9.96%).

2-β-Anilinovinyl-7-methyl-1, 8-naphthyridine-N₁-methiodide (13) : An intimate mixture of (5) (0.3g) and diphenylformamidine(0.15g) was fused in oil bath at 85-90° for 20 mts. cooled, triturated with dil. HCl, filtered and washed with water. Red needles m.p. 249-50°(ethanol) (0.2g). (Found : C, 50.82 ; H, 4.88 ; N, 10.17. C₁₈H₁₈N₃I requires C, 51.11 ; H, 4.46 ; N, 10.04%).

2-(1,7-Dimethyl-1,8-Naphthyridine)-2-(1-methylquinoline) trimethincyanine iodide (15) : An intimate mixture of (13) (0.1g) and quinaldine methiodide (0.088g) was taken in acetic anhydride (5ml) and heated to dissolve the solids, then triethylamine(1ml) was added, refluxed for 2 hrs. cooled and the solid filtered (0.1g). Dark blue needles, m.p. 276-77° (ethanol). (Found : C, 59.02 ; H, 4.98 ; N, 8.72. C₂₅H₂₂N₃I requires C, 59.10 ; H, 4.71 ; N, 8.98%).

4-m-Nitrostyryl-7-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine : An intimate mixture of (3)(0.15g) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.14g) was taken in dry toluene (10 ml) and refluxed for 12 hrs. using a water separator. The volume was reduced by evaporation, and then allowed to stand overnight when yellowish white solid was obtained. Reddish brown needles, m.p. 172°. (toluene). (Found : C, 69.93 ; H, 4.66 ; N, 14.12. C₁₇H₁₃N₃O₃ requires C, 70.30 ; H, 4.46 ; N, 14.43%).

7-Methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-4-Carboxylic acid : The above styryl compound (0.3g) was dissolved in acetone (25ml) and the solution cooled below 0° in

an ice bath. Finely powdered KMnO₄(1 g) was added portionwise to the solution with rapid stirring. After the addition was complete, the stirring was continued for an hour. The mixture was then rapidly warmed at 70° on a water bath, cooled and filtered. The solid obtained was washed with acetone, extracted with hot water (3 times, 5ml) and filtered. The combined extract was allowed to cool, acidified with conc. HCl and left overnight, when white crystals separated. This was filtered, dried and extracted with ether (3 times, 10ml) to remove any *m*-nitrobenzoic acid. The residue (0.1g) crystallised as white needles, m. p. 320° (aq. ethanol). (Found : C, 63.51 ; H, 4.60 ; N, 14.33. C₁₀H₈N₂O₂ requires C,63.84 ; H, 4.60 ; N, 14.85%).

Decarboxylation of acid :

The acid (0.2g) was mixed thoroughly with a trace of copper-bronze powder and heated above 300° in vacuum when a brownish white solid deposited on the cooler parts of the receiver. This was scraped out (0.05g). White needles of (1), m. p. 98-99° (Cyclohexane) (Lit¹. m. p. 99-100°. The m. p. was not depressed upon admixture with an authentic specimen.

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